

STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF LEXICAL UNITS RELATED TO INTERNATIONAL LAW IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of different models of terminological units in the language of international law and is based on the texts of 20 internationally recognized documents – International Labour Organization conventions. Due to the fact that conventions apply to different areas of international employment law, the terminology is thematically diverse. The authors distinguish three main types of terms depending on the number of components. Legal terminology is characterized by a certain semantic structure which is of great importance in conveying the meaning of the term. Special attention is given to the ways of legal terminology formation. Though legal English is rather conservative, it allows certain transformations by means of extension of meaning and at the expense of related fields of knowledge.

The study of interaction and interrelation of language and law has led to the formation of an independent area of research known as legal linguistics which is a relatively new area of research. It is a cross-disciplinary field of study as it combines the study of language and law / law and language in a number of contexts. In some contexts the language aspect prevails over the law (legal translation, legal lexicography, legal rhetoric), but in other contexts law becomes the starting point of research which is focused on legal terminology, the study of legal concepts, their interpretation within national legal systems and legislative drafting. Thus the language is perceived and exploited as a means of understanding, interpreting, and construing the communicative activity in legal sphere, both oral and written. The language of law has been in the focus of research of various disciplines since ancient Rome and ancient Greece. Besides linguistics, it was analyzed within such fields of knowledge as rhetoric, logics, philosophy, terminology studies. The first dictionary of legal terms – the lexicon was compiled by Gaius Aelius Gallus in the 1st century B.C. and is known under the title *De verborum quae ad jus pertinent significatione* (“On the meaning of words referring to the law”) (Fiorelli, 1947). Nevertheless, as a separate area of study legal linguistics developed only in the middle of the 20th century. The study of the functional style of legal language and the specifics of its usage

was centered on the issues of regulating and generating normative texts. These norms are viewed today as the basis of linguistic expert study of legal and normative acts.

Modern legal linguistics is represented by several sub-genres of legal language based on the varieties of types of lawyers and branches of law, which correlates with the research of German linguistic schools. These include the language of legal authors, legislators (laws and regulations), judges, administrators, advocates, notarial language; terminology of criminal law, land law, tax law, tort law, international law, etc. (Heikki, 2007). Each genre is characterized by its own domain of use and particular linguistic norms (phraseology, vocabulary, hierarchy of terms and meanings). In this regard, it is necessary to point out that legal language possesses a number of specific features. These are morphosyntactic, semantic, and pragmatic (Prieto, 1991). It is not fortuitous that legal language has become a research focus of various areas of linguistic studies as well as cross-disciplinary studies. One of the approaches to the analysis of legal language is the study of terminology. Understanding English legal terminology and translating it into other languages pose some difficulties because of the incongruity of legal systems which is stipulated by historical development and represents the specifics of legal thinking and ideology of different countries. The study of the language of law would be incomplete without taking into consideration recent methods and models of text analysis which are widely used in quantitative and corpus linguistics. For the purpose of this study, the authors find it reasonable to use context-based approach alongside statistical methods which allow one to automatically single out terms from the texts and rank them according to the structural models proposed by the authors. The presented article is a part of a wider project carried out by the Chair of English Language and Professional Communication at Pyatigorsk State University (Pyatigorsk, Russia) which is aimed at conducting multifaceted linguistic analysis of legal English. The project focuses on the following major objectives: checking contextual compatibility of lexical-semantic units in the language of international law; identifying terminological models and types; developing a linguistic model of legal English through the analysis of morphological-syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic specifics of the language of law. The article describes the results of the second stage of the project. The outcome of the study is a reliable bilingual (English-Russian) terminology resource, a Database of the terms of international law which contains 500 entries defining the type of term model, the field of knowledge the term belongs to, and the sphere of usage. The database is supposed to be interconnected with other databases developed in the course of the research conducted under the project. The first database has already been drawn by one of the authors of the article and at present is undergoing the registration process in the Russian patent agency "Rospatent" ("Database of English bigrams-collocations of the sphere of international law" compiled by O.M. Litvishko). The study involves several areas of linguistics – lexicology, lexicography, terminology studies, legallinguistics, with elements of quantitative and corpus linguistics. This allows the authors to implement a number of approaches, methods and techniques widely used by the areas of linguistics mentioned above. They include content-analysis and genre analysis (Legal linguistics, 2000), diversified search, frequency distribution, continuous sampling method (quantitative linguistics), semantic component analysis, descriptive method (lexicology). Using all these methods leads to the identification of terminological units with further analysis of their structural models. Data obtained in the course of the study are subject

to being classified with the help of statistical method. Using statistical method in text analysis appears to be of immediate interest when a new field of study is being developed, or when terminological system is being altered. This allows the researcher to highlight and evaluate terminological patterns. Legal linguistics, being a new area of linguistics, possesses extensive study material which has not been included into statistical text studies yet.

In the course of the analysis of the conventions of the ILO, it was observed that legal terminological units fixed in documents belong to other spheres, such as economics, politics, medicine, etc., in terms of their basic lexical meaning.

Thus in the texts of conventions, we see a number of economic terms, which is confirmed by their vocabulary definitions, in the paper we give only a few: salary – a fixed regular payment, typically paid on a monthly basis but often expressed as an annual sum, made by an employer to an employee, especially a professional or white-collar worker; tax – a compulsory contribution to state revenue, levied by the government on workers' income and business profits, or added to the cost of some goods, services, and transactions; employment – the state of having paid work (Oxford Dictionaries, 2000). This tendency is absolutely logical and can be easily explained. Here we need to take into account the basic mechanisms of term formation which are recognized in linguistics (Valeontis & Mantzari, 2006):

- creating new forms;
- using existing forms;
- translingual borrowing

The first and the third methods of term formation (creating new words and translingual borrowing) are not so widely spread in the sphere of law in general and in the texts of the ILO, in particular, due to its conventional and conservative nature and tight connection to the deep-rooted issues with long history. On carrying out the research, we came across a few examples (such as: *ipso jure*, *inter alia*) of borrowings from the Latin language, which had a great influence on further development of legal sphere. In the paper we pay our special attention to the second way of term formation which many scientists define as transdisciplinary borrowing or internal borrowing (Valeontis & Mantzari, 2006). It refers to situations where a designation from one specific subject field is used in another one in order to represent a different concept.

Within the framework of the research, the electronic database of English terms of the legal sphere, numbering 500 terminological units, was developed and registered in the Office of Innovativetechnological and project-oriented business activity of Pyatigorsk State University (Pyatigorsk, Russia). The database is of great practical value due to its dynamic nature and openness. It can be used by both legal professionals and ordinary citizens willing to have more profound knowledge of international employment law and be better equipped with legal issues.

References:

1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332087065_Structural_Peculiarities_Of_Terminological_System_Of_International_Law_Based_On_Ilo_Conventions/link/5c9ec8c4a6fdccd460439d71/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIn19;
2. Alimuradov, O.A., Latu, M.N., Razduev A.V. (2011). Features of structure and functioning of terminology (On the example of a terminology system of nanotechnologies). Pyatigorsk: Sneg

- Baranov A.N. (2007). Linguistic expert study of the text: theoretica underpinnings and practice. Moscow: Flinta Nauka
- Busse, D. (1999). Die juristische Fachsprache als Institutionensprache am Beispiel von Gesetzen und ihrer Auslegung, Fachsprachen. [The legal jargon as an institutional language using the example of laws and their interpretation, technical languages]. Ein international Handbuch zur Fachsprachenforschung und Terminologiewissenschaft. 2, 1382-1390;
3. Callanan, H., Edwards, L. (2010). Absolute Legal English. London: Delta Publishing;
 4. Cotterill, J. (2002). Language in the legal process. New York: Palgrave Macmillan;
 5. Coulthard, M. (1994). Advances in written text analysis. New York: Routledge.
 6. Coulthard, M., Johnson, A. (2007). An Introduction to Forensic Linguistics: Language in Evidence. London, New York: Routledge.